

Rac-3b

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xl-2-149-RAC-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	32	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 149 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	12.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/13/2021 6:22:14 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/13/2021 6:36:31 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.560	1410055	50.26	131259
2	9.304	1395491	49.74	

Asy-3b (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xl-2-150-2-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	1013
Vial:	67	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 150 2
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	12.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/13/2021 5:27:18 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/13/2021 6:31:19 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.609	240034	3.32	22034
2	9.377	6992894	96.68	445932